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Repair Landscapes

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Project Report

Cities are growing at an unprecedented rate, leading to a greater demand for resources. As we transition to new renewable energy sources and improve our construction and operational technologies to achieve net-zero emissions, it is crucial to prioritize repair and regenerative practices to mitigate cities' ecological footprint. Regenerative landscapes focus on environmental restoration by enhancing ecological dynamics and promoting biodiversity both below and above the soil. In this study, I explore a conceptual regenerative landscape design that not only aims to sequester carbon dioxide from building operations through soil processes but also encourages participatory care and governance by students in the UT School of Architecture. Gardening can and should be seen as a political act. It can play a central role in any biopolitical project, guiding ethical standards by forming connections with non-human living beings and establishing them as the foundation and boundaries of our design and planning practices.

Towards Repair Landscapes

Since 2021, over half of the world's 7.5 billion people have been residing in cities, leading to unprecedented land degradation and pressure on natural resources. In fact, the production of concrete, metal, plastic, bricks and asphalt is greater than the mass of living matter on the planet (1). The decline in the biosphere's regenerative capacity due to growing urbanization calls for more effective sustainability initiatives from multiple fronts (2). The building sector is responsible for 1/3 of current carbon emissions, and initiatives in the area are not only focusing on energy transition by updating energy codes and certification policies but also on the environmental impact of construction materials. Nevertheless, there is growing consensus that the ecological crisis we are facing today cannot be solved just by minimizing impacts through updated energy and building technology. Regardless of the upfront and operational environmental impacts of buildings, urbanization still leads to disturbance or destruction of soils.

Soils are the largest sinks for greenhouse gas emissions (CO₂, methane) (3). Recent studies have shown that global organic carbon storage in soils is 20 times the annual flux in the atmosphere, including anthropogenic CO₂ - which is a scary perspective if one considers the rate of soil degradation due to deforestation, growing urbanization and industrial agriculture. Soils are a complex yet fragile living systems that supports highly diversified ecological processes, above ground biodiversity, and hold social significance: soils provide food, underlying the identity of a place and its people. The idea of protecting soils, however, although essential, is not enough. Shifting towards regenerative and repair practices within the urban territory is fundamental for making cities sustainable, while contributing to climate stabilization.

This paper explores the significance of transitioning to soil-focused landscape management paradigms or “repair landscapes” by proposing a concept design to the UT School of Architecture Sutton Hall Building landscape. Despite advancing operational efficiency in buildings constructed before updated energy efficiency codes, as practitioners, we need to shift to systems that regenerate ecologies. In such an approach, the building environment and landscapes are viewed as complex adaptive systems across scales (from small buildings to city-scale) that can help cities mitigate current environmental pressures and extreme climate thresholds. In addition to enhancing biodiversity above and below ground and providing multiple ecosystem services, soil-based “repair” landscapes incorporate participatory, adaptive landscape management through community gardening. By adopting an environmentally sensitive planting and care through community gardening approach, there is a chance to change subjective perceptions on the appearance, evolution, and functioning of landscapes. This shift towards a community-led initiative for caring for landscapes can cultivate a sense of shared responsibility for the environment, including the soil and all its multitude of inhabitants.

*Sutton Hall. Tiles on the exterior vault.
Source: UT Blaker Alexander Collection. Unknown Photographer and date.*

The Place

Sutton Hall (1915-1918), formerly known as the Education Building, was designed by Cass Gilbert, UT campus architect at the time. The building showcases a Spanish Renaissance style, featuring brick and limestone facades and a hip roof covered in clay tile. Gilbert selected these materials for their practicality in the Texas climate and to pay homage to the state's history as a Spanish colony and Mexican territory. The intricate design of Sutton Hall includes wood carvings on the soffits, custom iron lanterns at the entrance, and decorative stone and terra cotta elements on the facade. One of the hall's standout features is the double vaulted arcade, adorned with vibrant ceiling mosaics. Gilbert's design is a celebration of craft, a rich visual experience in times of sleek and "cool" modern designs.

The building's landscape is a stark contrast to the intricacies of the historical Sutton Hall building design: vinca vine dominates the entire landscape except for patches of grass in areas with high sun exposure. However, some heritage live oaks (*Quercus virginiana*) dating back to the building's construction provide shade to the southern and western building's facades. Surrounding multi-story buildings, such as the Harry Ransom Center, Parlin and Calhoun Halls, shade most of the landscape during fall and spring, but not as much during summer. Southeastern winds are channeled between two of the surrounding buildings, making the Sutton Hall Garden a very sheltered place, ideal for more delicate planting schemes that invite close interaction. Finally, inefficient sprinklers are used for irrigation, keeping the bases of the oaks constantly wet and causing some of them to develop rooting issues.

Sutton Hall. South facade and main garden. March, 2024

Sutton Hall. West facade view. March, 2024

Sutton Hall. Southward view from 3rd floor studio. March, 2024

Sutton Hall Gardens irrigation. March, 2024

Sutton Hall Gardens, southward view. Lacey oak. March, 2024

Soils

The concept of ecosystem services, which highlights the nexus between ecosystems and social systems (human economics and wellbeing), seems to be inevitable to address the preservation and restoration of urban soils. Although evaluation approaches and quantification of soil's ecosystem services are still under development (4, 5), there is a consensus that soils support biodiversity and impact social-ecological systems in complex ways (6–8). Nevertheless, the design and management practices of urban green areas often come at a high environmental cost.

Urban landscapes commonly rely on oversimplified plant communities (e.g., lawn and “ornamental” non-native shrubs and trees) supported by centralized infrastructures for irrigation and wastewater management. Most urban green areas are maintained by gas-powered machinery and application of fertilizers, which can disrupt soil processes and lead to significant greenhouse gas emissions, making urban soils a source of CO₂ due to anthropogenic drivers. By examining how urban landscapes are managed, we are confronted with a challenging ethical question: if soils are alive, i.e., home to living organisms, how to design against ecological simplifications and environmental degradation? Designers, after all, should dismantle practices that are harmful to all living beings, including microorganisms living in soils.

Soil microbiomes are the least understood and most complex components of terrestrial ecosystems. Soil microorganisms mediate various aspects of the carbon cycle: microbes are responsible for much of soil respiration (9), most plant litter decomposition (10), and regulate plants metabolism via mutualisms and pathogens (11). Many studies suggest that microbial composition can affect entire soil-mediated ecosystem functioning by influencing key carbon pools, fluxes, and process efficiencies (12). Thus, landscape management that supports a living soil with thriving fungal and bacterial communities and high plant diversity will necessarily sequester carbon in soils.

The Design

Here I explore a concept landscape design that incorporates “keystone” native plant species into a few key components that promote below and above ground biodiversity, including i) in situ composting and water harvesting and soil infiltration, and ii) multi-story/high-diversity planting scheme (“tiny” understory forests) under heritage live oaks at the landscape. The concept of keystone species is formally applied to faunal species that play a critical role in maintaining the structure of an ecological community. However, I loosely incorporate this concept to define native plant species that support ecological processes and biodiversity, for example, by fixing nutrients in the soil or providing shelter and food to insects, birds and small mammals.

The multi-story/high-diversity planting scheme will include plant communities to create “pocket ecosystems” that include meadow-like patches with perennial and annual grasses and wildflowers in sunny areas “dotted” by tiny forests comprising understory brushes and small trees in more shaded areas underneath live oaks. Such “tiny” understory forests serve multiple functions: they mitigate soil compaction, increasing deep root aeration and water infiltration, and supports biodiversity below- and above-soil.

In addition to focusing on native plant species, the design incorporates in situ composting and water management through trenches along the terrain contour. The trenches are ~ 1’ deep and ~ 6’ wide, and will be used to place leaves, branches and wood chips harvested in the landscape, while serving to access paths to maintenance. Organic matter will build up in the trenches over time, stimulating soil’s fungi and beneficial bacteria to grow.

A garden that is constantly changing encourages us to reconsider the conventional, Cartesian distinction that separates culture from “nature”: culture, in fact, is inseparable from ecological dynamics. An ecologically minded gardening approach aims to enhance natural processes, but it is important to note that, despite its wild appearance, this is a man-made environment that supports soil processes and healthy plant growth. Over time, some grasses, shrubs, and trees may die or relocate. Gardening, nevertheless, should embrace these beneficial transformations, allowing the dynamics of change and regeneration linked to natural processes. This approach resonates from Gilles Clement’s “moving garden” approach, which can be summarized as “doing as much as possible with, and as little as possible against nature” (13).

Right: “Tiny” understory forests dotting the garden, underneath the heritage live oaks.
 Next page, left: Concept design for infiltration paths for on site biomass composting.
 Next page, right: Plan view of the Sutton Hall Garden, showing the proposed infiltration paths.

infiltration "paths"
• soil build up +
water mangement
soil biodiversity

Planting

The Sutton Hall building garden concept aims for a strong link to its native landscape of mature oaks on limestone plateau, though the garden is surrounded by buildings and not by an open landscape. In traditional gardens, obvious boundaries such as hardscapes and beds establish obvious separations between ornamental planting schemes. But with native perennials and grasses, whose textures are like those found at the Central Texas Hill Country's canyons and plateaus, there is no need for such articulation: the plants provide structure and year-round interest. In fact, such fine textures would be a great match to the Arts and Craft esthetics of the historical Sutton Hall Building. The only constraint that guided the planting scheme in the concept design was the plants' light requirements. While some species perform better as lower-light, understory species (e.g., *Cercis* sp.), others require at least 8h of direct sunlight to bloom (e.g., *Mahonia* sp.).

Shrubs and woody plants will articulate the space under the existing live oaks in the garden. These should include understory species that support soil and above ground biodiversity, such as the legumes *Bahuvia lunariodes* (anacacho), *Cercis americanus* and *C. texanus* (redbud), fruiting species such the *Callicarpa americana* (beautyberry), *Mahonia trifoliata* (agarita), *Diospyros texanus* (texas persimmon). These species should be densely planted and allowed to intermingle into compact understory groves, thus stimulating fast growth and biomass production.

A mid-layer beneath understory shrubs will include medium to tall shade-tolerant grasses (bluestem, wildrye grass and sea oat grama), while sunnier spots at the southern edge of the garden will have these same grass species intermingled with deep-rooted native perennials, such as cutleaf daisies, native sunflower, and native annuals, including the Texas bluebonnets.

- Q. virginiana*
- Q. laceyi*
- P. mexicana*
- M. grandiflora*

Right: Plan with existing trees in the Sutton Hall Garden

Next page, left: Concept design for low light/understory shrubs and small trees.

Next page, right: Concept design for full sun shrubs and small trees.

Muhly grass and tall goldenrod, early Fall.

Unripe Texas persimmon fruit, early Summer

Plateau goldeneyes, yucca, golden thread, Spring

Bluecurls, Indigofera, Opuntia, golden thread, Spring

*Aromatic summac (*Rhus aromatica*) and Cenizo (*Leucophyllum frutescens*), late Fall colors*

Ilex decidua, deciduous yaupon

Conspicuous in winter due to its many, small, red berries along leafless, gray twigs, that feeds mammals and birds.

Rhus aromatica, aromatic sumac

Aromatic sumac is a versatile native shrub: in Spring, fragrant flowers attract bees and butterflies and after first Fall frost, foliage turns red, yellow and orange. Only "female" specimens produce fruits, which are a treat to cardinals and other songbirds. Sumacs form thicket-like colonies, a shelter to small animals, from lizards to small birds.

Mahonia trifoliolata, agarita

Mahonias originated in North America 40 millions of ago and remain more or less unchanged in shape since then. This species has thorn-like trilobate leaves with a beautiful silver green hue. During Spring, bright yellow flowers are one of the first in the season to bloom and have an inebriating honey scent. Red berries are a favorite treat to many birds species.

Diospyros texana, Texas persimmon

Texas persimmons are a common understory small tree in the wild, but very underutilized in cultivated landscapes. Birds adore their black-fleshed, sweet fruits that ripe in July-August. This is one of the most elegant and yet resistant native trees in Central Texas.

Bauhinia lunarioides, Anacacho

Anacacho is endemic to Central Texas, occurring in very few bluffs and shaded valleys around Austin. It is an underutilized understory tree that has very fragrant white flowers in Spring and some year, early in Fall. As all legumes, anacacho benefits soil microbiota by supporting nitrogen-fixing bacteria on its roots.

La Dame à la Licorne, Musée de Cluny, Paris (detail). Source: Wikicommons

The Garden

I believe that tending to a garden gives me a unique understanding of the environment. By working the soil and interacting with nonhuman beings, visible and invisible, I gain a sense of immediate connection that may be biased but is ultimately rooted in respect for life. Gardening is a skill that can only be honed through practice and observation, making it a craft that informs (and is informed by) science, design and ethics.

Gardens can serve as a focal point for a community, bringing people together to care for and maintain the space using a variety of skills and talents. Gardens hold significance in a community, marking the passage of time and ensuring continuity. Trees grow, flowers bloom and fade, leaves fall, and new plants – whether welcomed or not – come and go. In Western culture, a *hortus conclusus* (enclosed garden) was once a place of thinking, productivity and regeneration. Think of the late 15th century tapestries of the *La Dame à la Licorne* now housed at the Musée de Cluny in Paris: a young woman is represented surrounded by everyday and mythological menagerie, including a unicorn, and orange trees with their flowers and fruits. Here, a garden is also a metaphor for spirituality and the senses. On the other hand, in Middle Eastern culture, gardens are a rejection of the sterility of deserts, offering water, sustenance, and spiritual enlightenment.

Gardens have always been associated with ideals, representing conceptual “tableaux” of nature governed by beauty and harmony. However, perceiving gardens as set landscapes that perform like programmed machines, renders them mere objects among other objects. Why should we rely on ecosystem simplification, mechanized routines and practices that harm and suppress nature, when gardens, which sustain life, deserve to be tended to with care and respect? At times of environmental crisis, gardens have become the best tool for the preservation of the commons: water, air, biodiversity and soil.

Nevertheless, there are no gardens without gardeners. Gardens serve as grounds for exploring horticulture, participatory governance, and ethics.

The Sutton Hall Garden has the potential to become a hub for participatory care provided by SOA students, who will learn gardening through hands-on experience, as well as through experimentation, sharing, and discovery. This organic interaction with the school’s landscape allows for a natural approach to maintenance by working in harmony with the ever-changing dynamics of the environment and plant communities. A gardening collective or guild within SOA could cultivate a garden that grows and evolves organically: a guerrilla garden in times when human connection with the environment is needed more than ever.

Finally, we, as practitioners, should reconsider our relationship with the environment through design. I firmly believe that there is still time to recognize new ways in which we can coexist and thrive with other species and move beyond linear exploitation-fabrication-assembly-disposal industrial logics and shift into an interspecies future, a new biopolitics, that makes all non-human lives the foundation and boundaries of our practices. We can start by gardening for future generations.

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